

Oxidation Studies. Part—XV : Ag(I)-Catalysis in Oxidation of Amines by Ce(IV) in Nitric Acid, A Kinetic Study

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The kinetics of Ag(I)-catalysed oxidation of methyl, ethyl, isopropyl, *n*-butyl, isobutyl, dimethyl and trimethyl amines by Ce(IV) was studied in nitric acid medium. The Ag(I)-catalysis of Ce(IV)-amine reaction is explained in terms of a 1 : 1 complex formation between Ag(I) and amine which later reacts with Ce(IV) bimolecularly to give the products. The rate law for the Ag(I)-catalysed oxidation of amines was found to be

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = \frac{kK[\text{Ce(IV)}][\text{amine}][\text{Ag(I)}]}{1 + K[\text{amine}] + K[\text{Ag(I)}]}$$

Ammonia and the corresponding aldehyde or ketone were identified as the products of oxidation of aliphatic primary amines, while formaldehyde and other amines were the products when dimethyl or trimethyl amines were the substrates. The activation parameters for the oxidation of amines are presented and discussed.

It is reported that amines could be oxidised using oxidants like permanganate¹, lead tetraacetate², cobaltic perchlorate³ and chlorinedioxide⁴. Recently, we reported⁵ the kinetics of oxidation of amines by Ce(IV) in nitric acid medium. It was shown in all these cases that amines could be oxidised by two distinct mechanisms, one involving dehydrogenation and the other by an attack at the lonepair electrons on nitrogen in the rate determining step. Even though Ag⁺ ions were found to be good catalysts, only sporadic references have been made in the literature about their use as catalyst in the oxidation of organic compounds by Ce(IV), specially in HNO₃ medium. In view of this, we have taken up a systematic kinetic study of oxidation of amines by Ce(IV) in presence of Ag⁺ to find out whether the presence of Ag⁺ ions results in a change in the mechanism of oxidation as also the mechanism of catalysis.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade. The method of following the kinetics was the same as reported earlier⁶. Approximate amount of ceric ammonium nitrate (AnalaR) was weighed and dissolved to give a ~0.10 M solution. The concentration was estimated by titrating against standard ferrous ammonium sulphate. This solution was diluted with nitric acid (0.50 M) to give 0.01 M solution. Salts of the general formula R.CH₂NH₂⁺NO₃⁻ were prepared by mixing one mole of amine with one mole of nitric acid. The silver nitrate used as catalyst was also of AnalaR grade.

Ammonia and corresponding aldehydes or ketones were the products of Ag⁺-catalysed oxidation of aliphatic amines while formaldehyde and other corresponding amines were the products when the dimethyl or trimethyl amines were used

as substrates. Ammonia was detected with Nessler's reagent. Formaldehyde and corresponding aldehyde or ketone were identified by their characteristic tests⁷ and further confirmed by m. p. of their 2,4-DNP derivatives.

Results and Discussion

Under the conditions of [Ce(IV)] ≪ [amine] in the presence of constant amount of Ag(I) the order in [Ce(IV)] was found to be unity. The pseudo first order rate constants (*k'*) were calculated from the slope of the linear plots of log [a/(a-x)] vs time [where, a and a-x are the concentrations of Ce(IV) at zero and time *t*, respectively]. The order in [amine] obtained from the plots of log *k'* vs log [amine] was found to be fractional. Increase in [Ag(I)] increased the rate and the order in [Ag(I)] was also fractional in all the cases (Table 1). Increase in [H⁺] or [NO₃⁻] decreased the rate of oxidation (Table 2). The reactions were studied in the temperature range 313-333°K to evaluate the activation parameters. Typical results with methylamine as the substrate are given in Tables 1 and 2 and Fig. 1. Induced polymerisation was observed when acrylamide was added to the reaction mixture.

Wylie employed⁸ the solvent extraction technique and suggested the existence of H₂[Ce(NO₃)₆] in moderately strong nitric acid solutions. Shorter⁹, who studied the oxidation of acetone by ceric nitrate in nitric acid assumed that Ce(OH)³⁺ was the reactive species. Similar conclusions were drawn by Mathur and Bakore^{10,11} in the oxidation of *sec*-butanol and *iso*-propanol. However, Sethuram and Muhammad⁶ and Santappa and Sethuram⁷ concluded from the effect of [NO₃⁻] and [H⁺] on the rate of oxidation of formaldehyde and some alcohols in nitric acid medium that the neutral Ce(NO₃)₄(H₂O)₂ was the most likely

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [Ag(I)] ON k' IN Ce(IV)-ALIPHATIC AMINE REACTIONS CATALYSED BY Ag(I)
 [Ce(IV)]=0.005 M ; [HNO₃]=0.500 M ; Temp.=333°K ;

Amine	$k' \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$							
	at [Ag(I)] mol dm ⁻³							
	0.010	0.015	0.020	0.030	0.040	0.050	0.060	0.080
Methyl (0.40 M)	6.10	—	8.69	—	13.9	—	19.3	25.3
Ethyl (0.80 M)	—	13.0	17.7	21.0	26.4	—	35.9	—
<i>n</i> -Propyl (0.20 M)	7.08	—	10.1	—	13.4	—	19.2	25.1
<i>iso</i> -Propyl (0.10 M)	2.65	—	5.00	—	9.60	—	12.0	16.8
<i>n</i> -Butyl (0.10 M)	14.8	—	20.3	26.4	31.0	39.5	—	—
<i>iso</i> -Butyl (0.40 M)	—	26.7	32.0	39.1	49.0	—	57.0	—
Dimethyl (0.20 M)	—	20.0	34.8	50.6	60.7	72.4	79.4	—
Trimethyl (0.10 M)	10.7	—	14.0	17.3	21.4	23.7	—	—

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF [NO₃⁻] AND [H⁺] ON Ce(IV)-*n*-PROPYLAMINE REACTION CATALYSED BY Ag(I)

 [Ce(IV)]=0.005 M ; [HNO₃]=1.00 M ; [Ag(I)]=0.020 M ;
 [*n*-propylamine]=0.200 M ; Temp.=328°K

Salt or [Acid] mol dm ⁻³	$k' \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	
	(NO ₃ ⁻)	(H ⁺)
0.400	22.4	20.4
0.800	16.6	17.0
1.20	12.6	13.9
1.60	10.2	11.7
2.00	8.70	10.0
2.40	5.90	9.00

reactive species of Ce(IV). The probable species that could exist in nitric acid solutions of Ce(IV) are Ce(NO₃)₆²⁻, Ce(NO₃)₅⁻, Ce(OH)(NO₃)₄⁻ and Ce(NO₃)₄ at fairly high [nitrate ion]. The choice of the reactive species was rather difficult but the fact that the rate of oxidation of amines by Ce(IV) in nitric acid was retarded by NH₄NO₃ coupled with the fact that the oxidation in perchloric acid medium was inhibited by the addition of nitrate ions indicated that the reactive species might be the neutral ceric nitrate molecule Ce(NO₃)₄ or more correctly Ce(NO₃)₄(H₂O)₂. The presence of

Fig. 1

- (A')—Plot of $\log [a/a-x]$ vs time, [Ce(IV)]=0.005 M, [HNO₃]=0.500 M, [Ag(I)]=0.020 M, [methylamine]=0.300 M ; temp.=333°K
 (A, B and C)—Plots of $1/k'$ vs $1/[\text{methylamine}]$ at temp. 318, 323 and 328°K, respectively [conditions same as in (A')]
 (D)—Plot of $(2 + \log k')$ vs $(1/T \times 10^3)$ [conditions same as in (A')]
 (E)—Plot of $(3 + \log k')$ vs $(1 + \log [\text{methylamine}])$ [conditions same as in (A')]
 (F)—Plot of $(3 + \log k')$ vs $(3 + \log [Ag^+])$ [conditions same as in (A')]

species $[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{NO}_3)_4]^-$ could not be discounted, though at high acid concentrations employed in the present work these hydroxylated species could be neglected. The inverse dependency of rate on $[\text{NO}_3^-]$ may be explained if one assumes neutral $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ to be the reactive species according to the following equilibria

In the presence and absence of Ag^+ it was found that H^+ ions inhibit the reaction. This could be either due to the hydrolysed species acting as the reactive species

$\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \rightleftharpoons [\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_4(\text{OH})\text{H}_2\text{O}]^- + \text{H}^+$
or due to the presence of equilibrium of the type

with $\text{R}-\dot{\text{N}}\text{H}_2$ as the reactive species. To find out whether hydrolysed species is the reactive one, we have studied the effect of $[\text{H}^+]$ on the oxidation of *n*-propanol, where the protonation equilibrium is not likely. It was found that increase in $[\text{H}^+]$ increases the rate of oxidation of *n*-propanol indicating clearly that hydrolysis equilibrium exists and that neutral ceric nitrate is the reactive species. Since $[\text{Ce}(\text{IV})]$ and $[\text{HNO}_3]$ are the same in the amines oxidation, we believe that in this case also the unhydrolysed species is the reactive one. The inhibition of H^+ ions on the amines oxidation could therefore be attributed to the removal of reactive free amine by protonation.

It was reported⁵ that in the absence of $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$ the order in [amine] is unity. The fractional order in [amine] in presence of $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$ indicated that it may be involved in complex formation either with $\text{Ce}(\text{IV})$ or $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$. Spectral studies in the present study indicated no complexation between $\text{Ce}(\text{IV})$ and aliphatic amine in conformity with our earlier observations⁶. Induced polymerisation due to the addition of acrylamide indicated the formation of the free radicals. $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$ is known to form colourless adducts with organic compounds^{1,2}. Therefore, the formation of an adduct between $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$ and amine, before oxidation by $\text{Ce}(\text{IV})$ in a slow step to yield Ag^{2+} -amine adduct, is proposed. If the adduct formation is taken as the first step, the reaction scheme for $\text{Ce}(\text{IV})$ -amine reaction in the presence of $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$ could be written as follows:

From the above mechanism, the rate equation comes out to be

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{2.303 d \log[\text{Ce}(\text{IV})]}{dt} &= k' \\ &= \frac{kK[\text{amine}][\text{Ag}(\text{I})]}{1 + K[\text{amine}] + K[\text{Ag}(\text{I})]} \quad \dots (1) \end{aligned}$$

where k' is the observed pseudo first order rate constant, k the bimolecular rate constant for the slow step and K the formation constant of $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$ -amine adduct. Equation 1 accounts for the observed fractional order dependence of rate in $[\text{amine}]$ and $[\text{Ag}(\text{I})]$. At constant $[\text{Ag}(\text{I})]$, we get the equation 1 modified as below:

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{[\text{amine}]} \left[\frac{1}{kK[\text{Ag}(\text{I})]} + \frac{1}{k} \right] + \frac{1}{k[\text{Ag}(\text{I})]} \quad \dots (2)$$

It is clear from equation 2 that plots of $1/k'$ vs $1/[\text{amine}]$ at constant $[\text{Ag}(\text{I})]$ should be linear. Such plots were obtained in the present work for all the amines studied (Fig. 1). From the intercept and slope values, the bimolecular rate constants, k , and the formation constants, K , for $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$ -amine adduct were evaluated at different temperatures and the various activation parameters calculated (Table 3).

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR $\text{Ce}(\text{IV})$ -AMINE REACTION CATALYSED BY $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$

Amine	$k \times 10^3$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1}$ (at 328°K)	K $(\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1})$	E_{exp} kJ mol^{-1}	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol^{-1}	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ $\text{J deg}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ $\text{J deg}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
Methyl	1.78	1.40	45.0	42.3	90.6	113
Ethyl	3.27	3.12	77.0	74.3	89.0	45
<i>n</i> -Propyl	3.79	4.33	44.0	41.3	88.6	146
<i>n</i> -Butyl	5.25	4.98	59.5	56.8	87.7	96
<i>iso</i> -Propyl	5.95	6.93	76.5	73.8	87.4	42
<i>iso</i> -Butyl	4.17	6.15	63.5	60.8	88.3	85
Dimethyl	18.5	9.20	44.8	42.1	84.8	130
Trimethyl	5.90	6.70	72.5	69.8	87.4	54

It was observed in the present study that the electron releasing groups accelerate the formation of adduct between $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$ and aliphatic amine, the order of reactivity being $\text{Me} < \text{Et} < \textit{n}\text{-prop} < \textit{n}\text{-but} < \textit{i}\text{-but} < \textit{i}\text{-prop}$. It was also observed that increase in the length of the carbon chain of amine had little effect on K whereas increase in the number of methyl groups on α -carbon atom had a significant effect (Table 3). These results could explain the

ease of formation of adduct between Ag(I) and aliphatic amine as the α -carbon atom to the amine group becomes more and more electron rich. This in turn facilitates the reaction between the adduct and Ce(IV) in the rate determining step.

Applicability of Taft's equation :

To study the applicability of Taft's equation for all the primary amines log K values were plotted against σ^* values at 323°K according to the general equation

$$\log(K/K_0) = \rho^* \sigma^* + \delta E_s \quad \dots (3)$$

where K and K_0 represent the formation constants of Ag(I)-adducts of substituted amines and methylamine, respectively, σ^* and E_s the polar and steric substituent constants, and ρ^* and δ the reaction constants for the same two effects, respectively. Using the standard least square method of bivariate linear regression¹³ the reaction constants due to the polar ρ^* and steric δ effects were found to be -3.37 ± 0.04 and -0.195 ± 0.02 , respectively. It was found that the formation constants for all the amines studied could satisfactorily be fitted into equation 3, using the above values. From the values of the reaction constants ρ^* and δ it is evident that the polar effects are playing a major role in the formation of the adduct compared to the steric effects.

The activation parameters for all the amines studied may be explained on the basis of isokinetic relationship. The ΔH^* and ΔS^* are related by

the equation $\Delta H^* = \Delta H_0 + \beta \Delta S^*$ where β is the isokinetic temperature. In the present study the plot of ΔH^* vs ΔS^* (Table 3) was linear with a slope equal to 380°K which is the isokinetic temperature, β , for this reaction series. The value is found to be much above the temperature range used (313-333°K) in the present study suggesting that the reactions are enthalpy controlled.

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